

Stability constants and thermodynamics of complexation of Schiff base hydrazones derived from 3-hydrazino-6-phenylpyridazine and acetophenone derivatives

Hussein Sakr Seleem

Ain Shams University, Faculty of Education, Chemistry Department, Roxy, Cairo, Egypt

Manuscript received 8 March 2002, revised 20 January 2003, accepted 31 January 2003

The acid-base equilibria and metal ion chelating tendency of 3-(acetophenonehydrazone)-6-phenylpyridazine (AHP) and its *para*-substituted derivatives (XAHP); X = NH₂, Cl, OH and OMe have been investigated potentiometrically in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water at 298 K and 0.1M KNO₃. For the same metal ion, the order of stability decreases in the sequence : NH₂AHP > OHAHP > OMeAHP > AHP > ClAHP, which is the same order of decreasing the electron-repelling property of the substituent (X) and consequently the basicity of the ligands. The thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated.

As a continuation of our interest in the thermodynamics of complexation of hydrazone- β -diketones¹, Schiff base hydrazones containing the pyridazine moiety^{2,3}, the triazine moiety⁴ and the pyrimidine moiety⁵ and in view of the biological activity of these ligands⁶, we report herein dissociation and stability constants for some Schiff base hydrazones (NN-donors) of 3-hydrazino-6-phenylpyridazine with acetophenone and its *para*-substituted derivatives (Str. I, II). Also, the thermodynamic functions for one selective ligand (NH₂AHP) as an example and its complexes with Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water were evaluated and discussed.

X	Abbreviation
H	AHP
NH ₂	NH ₂ AHP
Cl	ClAHP
OH	OHAHP
OMe	OMeAHP

Results and discussion

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand equilibria :

A representative set of the potentiometric titration curves of the free and complexed NH₂AHP ligand as a typical example in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water is given in Fig. 1. The curves were explained on the basis of the monoprotic nature of these ligands and the formation of two mononuclear species^{2,3}; ML⁽ⁿ⁻¹⁾⁺ and ML₂⁽ⁿ⁻²⁾⁺. The correction for the measured pH-values was taken⁷ as 0.28. The dissociation and stability constants as well as the thermodynamic functions were calculated as described earlier¹⁻⁴.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves of 3×10^{-3} M NH₂AHP in presence and absence of 1×10^{-3} metal ions.

It is to be mentioned that only $\log K_1$ for Cu^{II}-complexes was calculated since the maximum $\bar{n} \approx 1.0$. Also, in case of the Fe^{III}-complexes, a turbidity was observed in the titration vessel after $m = 1.0$ ($m =$ moles of KOH/mol of Fe^{III} ion). The dissociation constants of the ligands and their stepwise stability constants with the metal ions in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water at 298 K and 0.1 M KNO₃ are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Stepwise stability constants^a and statistical data ($\log K_1$)^b for the metal chelates

 Temp. = 298 K, solvent : 75% (v/v) dioxane-water, ionic strength = 0.1 M (KNO₃)

M ⁿ⁺	X = H		X = Cl		X = OH		X = OMe		X = NH ₂		-ρ ^c	r ^d
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂								
H ⁺	12.93 (12.99)	-	12.79 (12.82)	-	13.36 (13.27)	12.17	13.30 (13.20)	-	13.39 (13.49)	-	0.757	0.943
Mn ²⁺	6.77 (6.84)	6.44	6.71 (6.71)	6.31	7.11 (7.04)	6.83	7.07 (6.99)	6.80	7.12 (7.20)	6.85	0.548	0.932
Fe ³⁺	13.02 (13.11)	-	12.91 (12.92)	-	13.50 (13.41)	-	13.42 (13.33)	-	13.55 (13.64)	-	0.815	0.950
Co ²⁺	8.31 (8.36)	8.09	8.22 (8.22)	8.0	8.62 (8.58)	8.41	8.57 (8.52)	8.39	8.70 (8.75)	8.45	0.590	0.973
Ni ²⁺	8.50 (8.49)	8.03	8.35 (8.38)	8.12	8.70 (8.66)	8.54	8.63 (8.61)	8.47	8.75 (8.79)	8.59	0.461	0.976
Cu ²⁺	12.02 (12.12)	-	11.90 (11.92)	-	12.54 (12.45)	-	12.51 (12.36)	-	12.60 (12.71)	-	0.896	0.937
Zn ²⁺	8.17 (8.23)	7.86	8.06 (8.08)	7.81	8.53 (8.50)	8.35	8.50 (8.40)	8.43	8.55 (8.64)	8.39	0.624	0.932
Cd ²⁺	7.22 (7.23)	6.92	7.15 (7.16)	8.03	7.37 (7.35)	7.18	7.34 (7.32)	7.19	7.41 (7.44)	7.27	0.311	0.978

^aPotentiometrically. ^bThese values were obtained by linear regression of $\log K_1$ vs σ_x . ^cSlope of Hammett's equation ($\log K_x = \log K_{11} + \rho\sigma_x$). ^dCorrelation coefficient.

Inspection shows that the stability constants ($\log K_1$) for all ligands with the different metal ions follow the order : Fe^{III} > Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II} > Mn^{II}. This sequence has also been reported for aminopolycarboxylic acids⁸. The regularity of this stability sequence can be correlated with a monotonic increase in the second ionization potential and a monotonic decrease in the ionic radii⁹. Also, the stability constants ($\log K_1$) for the same metal ion with the different ligands decrease in the sequence : NH₂AHP > OHAHP > OMeAHP > AHP > ClAHP >, which is the same order of decreasing the basicity of the ligands, i.e. the basicity of the ligands is the main factor governing the stability of the chelates.

Substituent effect and Hammett's equation :

For the same metal ion, linear plot of $\log K_1$ vs σ_x (Hammett's constant) was obtained with a correlation coefficient (r) of *ca.* 1. The statistical results are presented in Table 1. The negative slopes (ρ) of the Hammett's equation reveal that the complexation (chelation) process is favoured by electron-repelling groups. This is because the *para*-substituents result in change in the basicity of the ligands and this in turn results in different stability constants of the chelates.

In an attempt to gain further information about the dependence of the stability of the chelates on the basicity of

the ligands, a linear regression analysis of $\log K_1$ for the substituted derivatives vs $\log K_1$ for the unsubstituted compound, AHP, was performed. The following relations were obtained in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at 298 K with a correlation coefficient (r) of *ca.* 1 and a slope amounting to about unity :

$$\log K_1(\text{NH}_2\text{AHP}) = -0.058 + 1.048 \log K_1(\text{AHP});$$

$$r = 0.9995$$

$$\log K_1(\text{OHAHP}) = -0.064 + 1.044 \log K_1(\text{AHP});$$

$$r = 0.9994$$

$$\log K_1(\text{OMeAHP}) = -0.077 + 1.040 \log K_1(\text{AHP});$$

$$r = 0.9993$$

$$\log K_1(\text{ClAHP}) = -0.045 + 0.994 \log K_1(\text{AHP});$$

$$r = 0.9999$$

However, these data effectively validate the Irving-Rossotti equation¹⁰ when structurally similar ligands are investigated.

Chelate effect :

The studied ligands act as bidentate (NN-donors) and form five-membered chelate rings. The effect of such chelate ring size can be illustrated by comparing $\log \beta_2$ for NH₃-complexes with $\log K_1$ for the studied ligand complexes, i.e. we compare values where two N-atoms are coordinated in each case. As $\beta_2 = K_1K_2$ or $\log \beta_2 = (\log K_1$

Table 2. Thermodynamic functions for the metal chelates of NH_2AHP ligand in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water and 0.1 M KNO_3

M^{n+}	288 K		298 K		308 K		318 K		ΔG , kJ mol^{-1}		ΔH , kJ mol^{-1}		ΔS , $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$		% $T\Delta S/\Delta G$	
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$-\Delta G_1$	$-\Delta G_2$	$-\Delta H_1^0$	$-\Delta H_2^0$	ΔS_1	ΔS_2	$T\Delta S_1/\Delta G_1$	$T\Delta S_2/\Delta G_2$						
H^+	13.60	-	13.39	-	13.10	-	12.87	-	-76.40	-	-44.30	-	-107.72	-	-	-
Mn^{2+}	7.30	7.07	7.12	6.84	6.92	6.60	6.73	6.06	40.63	39.03	34.11	37.07	21.88	6.58	16.05	5.02
Fe^{3+}	13.79	-	13.55	-	13.28	-	13.05	-	77.31	-	44.49	-	110.13	-	42.45	-
Co^{2+}	8.87	8.64	8.70	8.45	8.49	8.25	8.34	8.11	49.64	48.21	32.18	32.02	58.59	54.33	35.17	33.58
Ni^{2+}	8.92	8.84	8.75	8.59	8.58	8.33	8.40	8.13	49.93	49.01	30.89	42.74	63.89	21.04	38.13	12.79
Cu^{2+}	12.82	-	12.60	-	12.40	-	12.17	-	71.89	-	38.38	-	112.45	-	46.61	-
Zn^{2+}	8.68	8.63	8.55	8.40	8.39	8.28	8.26	8.15	48.79	47.93	25.37	29.98	78.59	60.24	48.0	37.45
Cd^{2+}	7.57	7.40	7.41	8.27	7.25	7.13	7.09	7.0	42.28	41.48	28.58	23.94	45.97	58.86	32.40	42.29

^aValues in parentheses are the correlation coefficients.

+ $\log K_2$) = 7.7, 5.0, 4.8 and 3.7 for Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} and $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{-NH}_3$ complexes¹¹, respectively. It will be seen that $\log K_1$ (Table 1) for the corresponding complexes is uniformly greater than $\log \beta_2$ for NH_3 -complexes. This is due to the chelate effect.

Temperature effect and the thermodynamic functions :

The dissociation and stability constants of NH_2AHP ligand and its complexes with Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions have been evaluated at 288, 298, 308 and 318 K potentiometrically in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water. A linear regression analysis of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ was utilized to evaluate the enthalpy change (ΔH). The resulting values are given in Table 2. Inspection shows that the dissociation of NH_2AHP is non-spontaneous, endothermic and entropically unfavourable while its complexation is spontaneous, exothermic and entropically favorable. This means that the dissociation of NH_2AHP is favourable at higher temperatures while its complexation is favourable at lower temperatures. This is in accordance with our previous studies¹⁻⁴.

From Table 2, it can be seen that the ΔH values associated with K_1 are in general similar to that of K_2 , but the entropic contribution (ΔS) differs strongly. According to Linert *et al.*¹², the formation of octahedral species is more exothermic. Hence, the lower negative values of both ΔH_1 and ΔH_2 for Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes may be attributed to

the formation of tetrahedral species. In order to decide whether ΔH or ΔS is the driving force for such chelation the percent ($T\Delta S/\Delta G$) has been calculated (Table 2). As seen, both the enthalpy and entropy terms are the driving forces except for Mn^{II} -chelates (1 : 1 and 1 : 2; M : L) and Ni^{II} -chelates (1 : 2; M : L only) where the enthalpy term is the only driving force.

Experimental

All chemicals, metal nitrates and solvents were either Aldrich, B.D.H. or Merck products. Apparatus, general conditions, purification of dioxane and methods of calculation were the same as in previous investigations¹⁻⁴.

Mass spectra were recorded at 70 eV on a GC/MS Finnigan mat SSQ 7000 spectrometer at the National Research Centre, Dokki, Cairo, Egypt. C, H and N were analysed on a Heraeus analyzer at the Microanalytical Centre, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt.

Metal nitrate solutions (0.01 M) were prepared in double-distilled water and standardized against EDTA. The ligand solutions (0.01 M) were prepared in dioxane. An 1 M KNO_3 solution was prepared in double-distilled water. A carbonate-free KOH solution (0.09 M) in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water was used as a titrant and standardized against oxalic acid.

Preparation of the ligands :

The ligands were prepared according to our previous work^{2,3}. An ethanolic solution of 3-hydrazino-6-phenylpyridazine (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 1 h with the stoichiometric amount of acetophenone or its *para*-substituted derivatives (0.01 mol) to yield the corresponding Schiff base hydrazones. The yellow crude products were filtered off, washed with ethanol, air-dried and crystallized from ethanol (yields 75–85%). The m.ps. of the ligands are as follows : AHP (C₁₈H₁₆N₄), 200°; NH₂AHP (C₁₈H₁₇N₅), 130°; ClAHP (C₁₈H₁₅N₄Cl), 206°; OHAHP (C₁₈H₁₆N₄O), 217°; OMeAHP (C₁₉H₁₈N₄O), 188° (Ref. 3). All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Potentiometric measurements :

Appropriate aliquots of standard solutions of metal nitrates (0.001 M) and ligands (0.003 M) in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water were titrated potentiometrically with 0.09 MKOH solution. For each mixture the volume was made up to 30 ml. The ionic strength of the medium was kept constant at 0.1 MKNO₃. A DIGI-520 pH-meter fitted with a combined glass-calomel electrode was used. Oxygen-free nitrogen was bubbled through the titrating solutions to keep the atmosphere inert.

References

1. A. T. Ramadan, M. S. Abdel-Moez, B. A. El-Shetary and H. S. Seleem, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1994, **131**, 103.
2. B. A. El-Shetary, M. S. Abdel-Moez, S. Abo El-Wafa, F. I. Zidan and H. S. Seleem, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1987, **119**, 249.
3. M. S. Abdel-Moez, S. Abo El-Wafa, H. S. Seleem and B. A. El-Shetary, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1989, **149**, 317.
4. A. T. Ramadan, M. F. Eid, H. S. Seleem and M. Mahmoud, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1995, **258**, 219.
5. S. M. Khalil, H. S. Seleem, B. A. El-Shetary and M. Shebl, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2002, **55**, 883.
6. M. A. Mahran, M. A. El-Sherben, M. A. Abdul-Rahman and B. A. Farid, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1998, **12**, 39.
7. H. M. Irving and U. S. Mahnot, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1215.
8. B. S. Gary and V. K. Jain, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1989, **146**, 375.
9. P. K. Sharma and S. K. Sindhwani, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, **135**, 211.
10. H. M. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, **10**, 72.
11. K. M. Mackay and K. A. Mackay, "Introduction to Modern Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Thomson Litho Ltd., Scotland, 1981.
12. W. Linert, A. Taha and Y. Fukuda, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1994, **33**, 235.